

COMPARISON OF PD CALIBRATION CAPABILITIES IN FOUR NATIONAL METROLOGY INSTITUTES DOWN TO 0.1 pC

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Abstract: Modern commercial PD calibrators often have their lowest charge level as 0.1 pC. However, now National Metrology Institutes (NMIs) provide traceable calibration services for apparent charge starting from 0.5 pC upwards and the relative uncertainty at this level is typically 20 %.

The main problem with the widely used numerical calibration method proposed in the standard is its low signal to noise ratio, which limits the accuracy on low PD levels below 10 pC. In practice, the lower limit of meaningful calibration work using this method is c. 1 pC. Charge sensitive amplifiers have been recently introduced for low PD calibration in the participating NMIs, and significant improvement in low-level calibration uncertainty has been achieved using this method.

This paper describes the results of a comparison between four NMIs. The aim was both to confirm their existing claims for measurement uncertainty from 1 pC to 50 nC, and to provide support for their plans to improve calibration services the low PD levels down to 0.1 pC.

The comparison was performed by transporting a reference calibrator between the four participating NMIs. Each NMI calibrated the 18 fixed settings of the PD calibrator, ranging from 0.1 pC to 50 nC. Values for measured charge, rise time, time to steady state and step voltage duration, as defined in current version of IEC 60270, were compared.

1. Introduction

Modern commercial partial discharge (PD) calibrators often have their lowest charge level as 0.1 pC. However, now National Metrology Institutes (NMIs) provide traceable calibration services for apparent charge starting from 0.5 pC and the smallest relative uncertainty at this level is 3 % [1]. Uncertainties below 1 pC are usually one order of magnitude higher than the uncertainties that are given for the charge levels above 10 pC.

IEC 60270 describes three methods for calibration of partial discharge (PD) calibrators. The reference method is by comparison with a reference calibrator. Second method is to use numerical integration method, where a PD calibrator is connected to a reference resistor, and the measured voltage signal is numerically integrated. The third approach is the step voltage method, where a PD calibrator is connected to a measuring capacitor and the voltage is measured over the capacitor using a digitizer.

In this work, four NMIs compared their capabilities for calibration of PD calibrators. The main objective was to compare their lately set up capabilities for low level PD calibration down to 0.1 pC. Two additional objectives can be identified. This ad hoc comparison was used to gather experience on the

performance of the transfer reference calibrator for more formal comparison, which is currently under consideration within EURAMET. In addition, the participating NMIs got support for their existing uncertainty claims for higher PD values, possibly also for their improvement.

BIPM key comparison database lists the mutually agreed calibration uncertainties for NMIs. For the participating NMIs the uncertainties range from 0.1 pC to 0.6 pC for apparent charge below 10 pC. For higher apparent charge values above 10 pC the uncertainties are between 2 % and 3 % [1].

2. Overview of calibration methods

Different methods have been proposed for calibration of PD calibrators. The following listing is based on IEC 60270 [2]. The described methods can also be combined.

2.1. Comparison with reference calibrator

The schematic structure of a typical reference calibrator is shown in Figure 1. In the figure from left are the DC voltage source, charging resistor R_{sg} , mercury-wetted relay, voltmeter V and the injection capacitor C_0 . The voltmeter is used to measure the charging voltage U_0 . Connectors are shown by dotted lines, and C_1 and C_2 are stray capacitances.

The influence of C_1 can be ignored, as it is shorted by the mercury relay when an impulse is applied. When used with charge amplifier or with integration method, C_2 can be ignored, as the voltage across it finally returns to zero. In this case the apparent charge can be calculated from

$$q = C_0 U_0 \quad (1)$$

Figure 1: Principle of a PD reference calibrator.

2.2. Step voltage method

In the step voltage method shown in Figure 2, injection capacitor C_0 is discharged into another capacitance C_m , and the step voltage across it, U_c , is measured. In this case C_0 , C_2 and C_m form a voltage divider. When using this method, it should be remembered that the capacitance of the connecting cable and the input of the voltage measurement instrument must be included either in C_2 or in C_m . The resistor R_s can be used to reduce oscillations. The charge can be calculated from

$$q = (C_2 + C_m) U_c \quad (2)$$

Figure 2: Principle of a step voltage method for calibration of PD calibrator.

2.3. Numerical integration

Measurement of the applied charge can be performed using the numerical integration method described in IEC 60270. As seen in Figure 3, the generated charge q flows through the shunt when the calibrator is connected to its terminals. This current $i(t)$ can be obtained by measuring the voltage $u_m(t)$ over the shunt resistor R_m . The generated charge can be calculated by integrating the current numerically as given in equation (3). The standard limits the current shunt R_m values to be within 50Ω to 200Ω and requires the digitizer to have a bandwidth higher than 50 MHz .

Figure 3: Principle of integration method.

The challenge with this method is the decrease of the signal to noise ratio, especially when the level of PD is reduced from 10 pC to lower levels.

$$q = \int i(t) dt = \frac{1}{R_m} \int u_m(t) dt \quad (3)$$

3. Comparison setup

3.1. Transfer reference

Fixed settings were used for the transfer reference calibrator [3]. 18 positive apparent charge values from 0.1 pC to 50 nC in 1-2-5 sequence were listed for comparison. The calibrator was set to deliver unipolar pulses with 50 Hz .

The preferred approach was to measure the average value of a minimum of 10 single shot charge values on each level. It was allowed to average more pulses in order to reduce type A uncertainty but averaging of several sweeps was not recommended.

Table 1: Comparison schedule

Participant	Dates
VTT1	6.-24.8.2018
LCOE	3.-7.9.2018
TÜBİTAK UME	8.-12.10.2018
RISE	22.-26.10.2018
VTT2	3.-7.1.2019

3.2. Applied calibration techniques

3.2.1. VTT

Three different measurement methods were used at VTT according to Table 2, depending on the apparent charge value. The charge sensitive amplifier was used up to its maximum range, 20 pC [4], [5], [8]. A high-speed amplifier for step voltage method was introduced for 50 pC to 2 nC range between the two VTT sessions, and it was used during the latter session. The scale factors of the charge and step voltage amplifiers were determined for each charge using a reference calibrator. All other measurements were performed with integration method using $50\text{-}\Omega$ resistor and digitizer with 500 MHz bandwidth and 1 GS/s sampling rate.

Table 2: VTT calibration methods

Range	VTT1	VTT2
0.1 pC - 20 pC	Charge amplifier	Charge amplifier
50 pC - 2 nC	Numerical integration	Step voltage method
2 nC - 50 nC	Numerical integration	Numerical integration

3.2.2. LCOE

Two different measurement methods were used at LCOE according to Table 3, depending on the apparent charge value. A charge sensitive amplifier was used from 0.1 pC up to its maximum range of 2 pC. Between 0.2 pC and 50 nC, the numerical integration method was used with an oscilloscope of 350 MHz bandwidth and a R_m value of 50 Ω . In the range from 0.2 pC to 2 pC both methods were used.

Table 3: LCOE calibration methods

Range	LCOE1	LCOE2
0.1 pC	-	Charge amplifier
0.2 pC - 2 pC	Numerical integration	Charge amplifier
2 pC - 50 nC	Numerical integration	-

3.2.3. TÜBİTAK UME

The measurements of TÜBİTAK UME were performed from 0.2 pC to 1000 pC using integration method (see Table 4). An oscilloscope of 600 MHz bandwidth and 2 GS/s sampling rate was used with R_m of 200 Ω [6].

Table 4: TÜBİTAK UME calibration methods

Range	TÜBİTAK UME
0.2 pC - 1000 pC	Numerical Integration

3.2.4. RISE

Two different measurement methods were used at RISE according to Table 5, depending on the apparent charge value. Two different charge sensitive amplifiers were used, one up to 20 pC, and the other up to 500 pC. The scale factors of the amplifiers were determined for each charge using a reference calibrator. For the higher charges the integration method was used with a 50 Ω shunt. In all cases, the voltages were captured using the same high-speed digitizer.

Table 5: RISE calibration methods

Range	RISE
0.1 pC - 500 pC	Charge amplifier
1 nC - 50 nC	Numerical integration

3.3. Comparison results

3.3.1. Apparent charge

The transfer reference calibrator was calibrated at VTT before (VTT1) and after (VTT2) it circulated in the other labs. The results as deviation from the comparison average value are shown in tabular format in Table 6. The same results are also shown in Figures 4 to 6. Small horizontal offsets have been applied to results for clarity of presentation. Note the logarithmic x-axis.

Table 6: PD calibration results. Differences are from average value.

Nominal charge Q_N [pC]	VTT1		LCOE1		LCOE2		UME		RISE		VTT2	
	Diff.	Unc.	Diff.	Unc.	Diff.	Unc.	Diff.	Unc.	Diff.	Unc.	Diff.	Unc.
0.1	-1.2 %	1.0 %			2.9 %	3.0 %			-0.6 %	0.6 %	-1.2 %	0.9 %
0.2	-1.0 %	0.8 %	-0.1 %	1.5 %	2.4 %	3.0 %	0.5 %	6.0 %	-0.6 %	0.6 %	-1.2 %	0.8 %
0.5	-0.5 %	0.8 %	-1.7 %	1.5 %	2.1 %	3.0 %	0.2 %	6.0 %	0.4 %	0.6 %	-0.4 %	0.7 %
1	-1.3 %	0.7 %	-1.7 %	1.5 %	3.0 %	3.0 %	1.1 %	6.5 %	0.0 %	0.5 %	-1.1 %	0.7 %
2	-0.8 %	0.7 %	-1.7 %	1.5 %	1.9 %	3.0 %	0.7 %	3.5 %	0.6 %	0.5 %	-0.7 %	0.7 %
5	-0.2 %	0.7 %	-0.6 %	1.5 %			-0.2 %	3.0 %	1.2 %	0.6 %	-0.3 %	0.7 %
10	-0.2 %	0.7 %	-0.9 %	1.5 %			0.2 %	2.0 %	1.2 %	0.5 %	-0.3 %	0.7 %
20	-0.3 %	0.7 %	-0.3 %	1.5 %			0.0 %	1.5 %	0.9 %	0.8 %	-0.3 %	0.7 %
50	0.2 %	1.9 %	-0.5 %	1.5 %			0.8 %	1.2 %	-0.2 %	0.8 %	-0.4 %	0.8 %
100	0.1 %	1.9 %	-0.2 %	1.5 %			0.7 %	1.1 %	0.0 %	0.8 %	-0.6 %	0.9 %
200	0.1 %	1.7 %	-0.4 %	1.5 %			0.5 %	1.1 %	0.2 %	0.8 %	-0.5 %	0.8 %
500	-0.1 %	1.9 %	0.2 %	1.5 %			0.0 %	1.0 %	0.0 %	0.8 %	-0.1 %	0.8 %
1000	0.2 %	1.8 %	-0.2 %	1.5 %			0.5 %	1.0 %	-0.5 %	1.0 %	-0.1 %	0.8 %
2000	-0.1 %	1.7 %	-0.4 %	1.5 %					0.6 %	0.8 %	-0.1 %	0.8 %
5000	0.0 %	1.8 %	0.4 %	1.5 %					0.0 %	1.0 %	-0.4 %	1.8 %
10000	0.6 %	1.9 %	-0.7 %	1.5 %					-0.1 %	0.9 %	0.2 %	1.9 %
20000	0.1 %	1.8 %	-0.3 %	1.5 %					0.2 %	0.8 %	0.0 %	1.8 %
50000	0.3 %	1.7 %	-0.3 %	1.5 %					0.2 %	0.8 %	-0.2 %	1.7 %

The results for the low ranges below 10 pC are shown in Figure 4. The laboratories using the integration method have significantly higher uncertainties than the laboratories using a calibrated charge amplifier. The middle range results from 10 pC to 500 pC are shown in Figure 5, and the agreement is well within 2 %, which is the lowest claim of the participating NMIs. The high range results from 1 nC to 50 nC are shown in Figure 6, and the agreement is again well within 2 %, which is the lowest claim of the participating NMIs.

Figure 4: Comparison results from 0.1 pC to 5 pC.

Figure 5: Comparison results from 10 pC to 500 pC.

Figure 6: Comparison results from 1 nC to 50 nC.

3.3.2. Time parameters

Results of time parameter measurements are shown in Table 7. The transfer function of the charge amplifier depends also on the impedance of the source it is measuring [7]. It was observed also during this project, that the rise time will increase with higher parasitic capacitance C_2 and with decreased gain bandwidth of the amplifier. In the case of integration method, the lower observable limit is often determined by the injection capacitor together with the shunt resistance and in some cases also an impedance matching series resistor in the calibrator. The charge amplifier used in this project claims 5 ns rise time [8].

Table 7: Measured time parameters for positive 1 pC output.

	Numerical integration		Charge amplifier					
	PD rise time		Step rise time		Step settling time		Step duration	
	t_r [ns]	u [ns]	t_r [ns]	u [ns]	t_s [ns]	u [ns]	t_d [μ s]	u [μ s]
VTT1			18.5	2	27.7	2	7.4	0.2
LCOE1	4.7	0.2						
UME	5.2	1						
RISE			22	1.8	30.1	1.3	7.05	0.15
VTT2			18.6	2	27.9	2	7.3	0.2

4. Conclusions

Using a charge-sensitive preamplifier is promising way to calibrate PD calibrators below 1 pC because it offers a higher signal level and good repeatability together with low noise level. Estimated uncertainty for measurements down to 0.1 pC is below 2 % ($k=2$), which is almost one order of magnitude lower than currently available from National Metrology Institutes. Conventional numerical integration approach has also demonstrated to be reasonable way to calibrate PD calibrators below 1 pC but not lower than 0.2 pC.

The results support the uncertainty claims of the participating laboratories well.

The commercial PD calibrator was easy to use, and it was stable enough transfer reference for this exercise

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The work reported here has received support from the EMPIR programme co-financed by the Participating States and from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme.

Identification of certain equipment does not imply recommendation by the authors, nor does it imply that the equipment is necessarily the best available for the purpose.

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